

Positive Reinforcement And Secondary School Students

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Abstract

The modern education system provides child centred method of teaching. But there is a gap line between students and teachers. So academic performance and life performance of students failing to reach the goal up to the mark. Even many teachers trying to reach students and many students trying to reach teachers. But this gap may not be filled without touching the heart of child. The motivation, encouragement matters for innocent smiles. So The present study focus on the concept 'positive reinforcement'. The study reveals that no significant difference was observed between government and private school teachers with respect to application of positive reinforcement scores ($t=-0.5658, p>0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. It means that, application of positive reinforcement scores are significantly does not differ with regard to male and female schools teachers. All teachers showed positive gesture towards application of positive reinforcement. A significant difference was observed between male and female secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement scores ($t=-2.2751, p<0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It means that, the positive reinforcement scores are significantly higher among female students as compare to male students of secondary schools. A significant difference was observed between government and private secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement scores ($t=-3.1842, p<0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It means that, positive reinforcement scores are significantly higher private schools as compare to government secondary schools. The study suggested that government secondary school students badly need motivation encouragement and acceptance.

Keywords: Compassion, Encouragement, Motivation, Reinforcement, Verbal

1. Introduction

The teacher manages the class with different kinds of techniques and skills. In teaching learning process students interacts with teacher. The teacher teaches topic with zeal of interest or in monotonous way. The success of innovative practices and activities depend on ability of teacher. The learner receives knowledge from teacher with interest some time without interest. If the teacher talk followed by students talk then there will be an interesting interaction process taking place. The students responses may correct or incorrect but teaching learning process move on. To bring spark in teaching learning, there must be some essence of learning spirit. The learning passion of students need to be enlighten by teacher. If teacher motivates or encourages child to learn more in academics then learner my increase in interest in learning or study habit or may increase in self regulating ability. The reinforcement or reward motivates child to do good in all area of life. The traditional old micro teaching method may increase skill of teacher also may increase rate of academic achievement and their life style.

Many students may need motivation, acceptance, affection not only from parents but also from teachers. The reinforcement and motivation to learn or to do any task is important on the part of learner. And teachers also need motivation, guidance. The present study focus on 'positive reinforcement.

2. Reviews

1. The study conducted by Kanchana Khatreja K.R Mangalam Institutions of higher education (may 2023) Abstract: Introduction Pavlov coined the term "reinforcement" in 1903. The concept of reinforcement refers to accomplishing work by providing incentives or rewards to a specific person. Any stimulus that strengthens, encourages, or increases the likelihood of a specific response is referred to as a stimulant. Definition of Reinforcement is an event that increases the likelihood of a response recurrence when a stimulus is produced in similar situations. It is an evidence-based practices for teaching specific skills and increasing

desired behaviour. Reinforcement refers to the use of such stimuli, or their presentation or removal, in order to increase the probability of achieving the desired outcome.

2. The study done by Komang Diah Kusuma Werdi, Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha, Indonesia and team given Abstract: This study aimed to identify the types of reinforcement skills and investigate the implementation of reinforcement skills used during the online learning process at SMP Laboratorium Undiksha Singaraja. This study used a qualitative descriptive method as the research design. This study also used an English teacher as the research subject. In collecting data, this study used three methods, namely; observation, interview, and questionnaires. This research was conducted online due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Through the data obtained, this study found the results of the type of reinforcement and the implementation used by teachers during online learning. There are four types of reinforcement used by the teachers, such as; (1) positive verbal reinforcement in the form of praise and partial reinforcement, (2) positive non-verbal reinforcement in the form of gestures, (3) negative verbal reinforcement in the form of enforceable statements, questions, calling out the students' names, and (4) negative non-verbal reinforcement in the form of facial expressions and record the students' misbehavior. In addition, the reinforcement implementation was relevant to the theories suggested by experts by following the five principles in giving reinforcement. Further study is needed to get a deeper understanding toward the implementation of reinforcement in EFL classroom.
3. The study conducted by N. N. S. Mandah O. L. Gbarato *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science Published: 2016-07-31 Page: 1-11 Issue: 2016 - Volume 17 [Issue 3] on the topic 'The Influence of Reinforcement Skill on Academic Performance of Secondary School Physics Students in Obio-Akpor Lga, Rivers State Nigeria' Abstract: This study is aimed at assessing the influence of reinforcement skill on the Academic Performance of Secondary School Physics students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, using three research questions and one hypothesis. The study which adopts the descriptive and quasi-experimental research design employed a sample size of sixty teachers and one hundred and twenty students of senior secondary One (SSI) in the sample Area. The questionnaire titled "Teachers Reinforcement Skill Questionnaire" (TRSQ) was part of the instrument and fundamentals of Measurement in Physics. The statistical mean was used to analyse the data for the research questions while standard deviation and Z-test were used to analyze the data to obtain the validity of the hypothesis. The findings revealed that some factors such as insincere reinforcement, adoption of only one form of reinforcement, among others, hinder proper application of reinforcement skill. It was also found that the use of reinforcement influences the academic performance of Physics students. Based on this, it was recommended that teachers should always apply reinforcement skill, be sincere in the application and attend training programmes on teaching skills.

3. Objectives

1. To study the interest teachers to apply positive reinforcement among secondary school students.
2. To study the influence of teacher's positive reinforcement on different location among secondary school students.

4. Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers with respect to application of positive reinforcement.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between government and private secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement.

5. Methodology

A. Data Collection

- a. The researcher conducted clinical interview for secondary school teachers who were working in government and private secondary schools of Koppal and Vijayapura district. The researcher organised discussion session for secondary school teachers and gave suggestions to apply positive reinforcement in their daily routine class. Total (60) teachers were involved in the discussion. They agreed to respond and only interested teacher were taken for study. They were given constructed items which were standardized with five validation process. total 21 questions provided which were checked reliability Chronbatcha alfa method. The data was calculated weekly interval of time continuously one semester. 30 private school teachers and 30 government school teachers responded.
- b. Among all students population only (200) two hundred secondary school studying 9th standard were acted as samples. To get response from students, stratified sampling method was applied.
- c. On 'reinforcement' items were constructed and standardized with six level of validation process. First level 400 items were constructed. The experts were suggested only three hundred. Again, for verification three hundred items were given for checking. The academicians were suggested only two hundred and the items were verified as per the indicators. So only hundred items validated for fourth level. At fifth level micro-teaching experts and B.Ed. college teacher educator verified suggested only fifty questions. At sixth level and only 21 items were finalised and standardized. The reliability was checked with Chronbatcha 0.8. The PR-items were followed by likert five point scale. The data was collected with well versed instructions. Interest of student is respected. The Mean SD T-test applied to compute data.

B. Data Analysis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school teachers with respect to application of positive reinforcement

Table 1: Results of t test between male and female secondary school teachers with respect to application of positive reinforcement

Group	n	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Signi.
Male	30	68.37	7.93	-0.5658	0.6212	
Female	30	69.72	8.02		>0.05	NS

The above table says that no significant difference was observed between male and female school teachers with respect to application of positive reinforcement scores ($t=-0.5658, p>0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. It means that, application of positive reinforcement scores are significantly does not differ with regard to male and female schools teachers. All teachers showed positive gesture towards application of positive reinforcement. All secondary school teachers responded well. They were happy to apply positive reinforcement in their class. During and after semester they saw there was drastic change in student’s life style and academic performance.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement

Table 2: Results of t test between male and female secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement.

Group	n	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value	Signi.
Male	100	79.37	8.93	-2.2751	0.0019	
Female	100	89.72	9.02		<0.05	S

The above table says that significant difference was observed between male and female secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement scores ($t=-2.2751, p<0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It means that, the positive reinforcement scores are significantly higher among female students as compare to male students secondary schools. The mean scores of positive reinforcements are given with graph in following figure.

Fig 1: Comparison of male and female secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between government and private secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement.

Table 3: Results of t test between government and private secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement.

Group	n	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Signi.
Government	100	63.31	6.61	-3.1842	0.0016	S
Private	100	78.63	8.02		<0.05	

A significant difference was observed between government and private secondary school students with respect positive reinforcement scores ($t=-3.1842, p<0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It means that, positive reinforcement scores are significantly higher private schools as compare to government secondary schools. The mean scores of positive reinforcement are given below with graph.

Fig 2: Comparison of government and private secondary schools with respect to positive reinforcement

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement.

Table 4: Results of t-test between rural and urban secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement

Group	n	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value	Signi.
Rural	100	81.47	8.03	-0.3923	0.7696	
Urban	100	82.81	8.19		>0.05	NS

No significant difference was observed government and private secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement scores ($t=-0.3923 >0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis is accepted. It means that, no difference found with regard to positive reinforcement scores among rural and urban school students. The mean scores of positive reinforcement with regard to rural and urban secondary schools given in following graph.

Fig 3: Comparison of rural and urban secondary schools with respect to positive reinforcement

6. Discussion and analysis

1. The study reveals that there is no significant difference observed between government and private school teachers with respect to positive reinforcement scores ($t=-0.5658$, $p>0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. It means that, application of positive reinforcement scores are significantly does not differ with regard to male and female schools teachers. All teachers showed positive gesture towards application of positive reinforcement. The teachers acted as samples shown better performance and has passion is teaching. But Generally in present scenario teacher are running to complete syllabus. There is need of motivation, acceptance, affection which may change life of students. The result reflects that the rate of improvement is high in academics and non academics also. It is essential motivation and encouragement for teachers also to apply positive reinforcement.

2. The study says that significant difference was observed between male and female school students with respect to positive reinforcement scores ($t=-2.2751$, $p<0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. It means that, response towards positive reinforcement scores are significantly higher in females as compare to male secondary school students. The female students responded well towards positive reinforcement. The item 'If you are praised by teacher by responding correct answer then are you spending whole day with happiness?' students responded 'strongly agree' where as male students responded 'neutral' This reflects that male students need more motivation and affection, compassion and care from teachers and parents

3. A significant difference was observed between government and private secondary school students with respect to positive reinforcement scores ($t=-3.1842$, $p<0.05$) at 5% level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It means that, response towards positive reinforcement scores are significantly higher among private schools as compare to government secondary schools. Hence private school students responded well towards positive reinforcement. like giving rewards for their correct answer. And positive verbal and non-verbal reinforcement influence positively on private school students as compare to government school. The government schemes and government teachers may applied many innovative methods in the class. Many technological methods of teaching followed by teachers and computer insisted materials may be used in the class. But computer never come to students and pat his back and encourage to learn. The non-living things never understand student's feeling. So, reinforcement in the class is very essential. In modern scenario students have been taught with many innovative methods. They may clear concept but the positive reinforcement inspires, and motivates and shapes the feeling of students and change student's life style. It is also observed that the students responded to the item 'Are you leading happy minutes after school with regard that your ideas accepted and rewarded in front of whole class? This reflects that the students need positive reinforcement to lead their life. It acts like tonic for their life mental diseases. So that every teacher should apply positive reinforcement in their class with respect to all subjects. Operant Conditioning: What It Is, How It Works, and Examples By Saul McLeod, PhD February 2, 2024 B.

F. Skinner's theory of operant conditioning describes positive reinforcement. In positive reinforcement, a response or behavior is strengthened by rewards, leading to the repetition of the desired behavior.

4. The study says that no significant difference was observed rural and urban secondary school students response towards positive reinforcement scores ($t=-0.3923>0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis is accepted. It means that, no difference found with regard to response towards positive reinforcement scores among rural and urban school students. This reflects that positive reinforcement both rural and urban students shown same answer. The responses analysed with regard to positive reinforcement like verbal and nonverbal act of teacher is accepted. Thriving Learners, Empowered Communities (2017) Elsa Balling and Alda Walqui 'Zone of Proximal development' a perspective teaching ell's the Zone of Proximal Development provides as the space between what a learner can do without assistance and what a learner can do with adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers. So the teacher can follow ZPD to improve not only academic performance but also life performance.

7. Suggestions/Recommendations

The same study can be conducted in primary and higher education level and other streams also teachers also need motivation and reinforcement. In other professional courses teachers are framed with strict rules and regulation and they implement same on students but positive reinforcement change lives of students.

The present study restricted to only two hundred students and sixty teachers and Koppal and Vijayapura district Karnataka, India, can be done in all districts and states and nations of the world. In present days students facing problems not only in academic but outside school also. A teacher's one step of acceptance and compassion with regard to academic will influence the non-academic life also.

A teacher is a friend philosopher and guide who can enlighten the path of his students. As for as reinforcement concerns teacher's act of positive reinforcement is path of light in the life of student. It is my suggestion all teachers in the world should apply positive reinforcement in their class. Whatever subject you teach please apply positive reinforcement. You can bring the smile on innocent students who might be in trouble not only academic but also outside the school.

8. Conclusion

The application positive reinforcement in daily class is very important on the part of teacher. Every teacher in the world should think about positive and reinforcement which may change world of student in current scenario. The positive reinforcement very essential whenever student does good work. It must be encouraged immediately. so the students will repeat good task again. Any punishable act also been guided with positively. Hence the art of applying positive reinforcement must be mastered by teacher to build better future.

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